

THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE JIZZAKH REGION

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Abstract. *Tourism is from the place of permanent residence of an individual visited for health, educational, professional-practical or other purposes without engaging in paid activities in the place (country). It is understood that he leaves (travels) for a period of one year. Jizzakh the number of companies and organizations carrying out tourist activities in the region is 11, and in 2020 they provided services to 18,500 visitors.*

Keywords: *company, organization, tourist activities, tourism sector.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТУРИЗМА В РАЗВИТИИ ДЖИЗАКСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация. *Туризм с места постоянного проживания физического лица, посещаемый с оздоровительными, образовательными, профессионально-практическими или иными целями без занятия оплачиваемой деятельностью в этом месте (стране). Понятно, что он уезжает (путешествует) сроком на один год. Джизак количество предприятий и организаций, осуществляющих туристическую деятельность в области, составляет 11, и в 2020 году они обслужили 18 500 посетителей.*

Ключевые слова: *предприятие, организация, туристическая деятельность, сфера туризма.*

INTRODUCTION

Hotels and similar in Jizzakh region in 2019 the number of persons placed in places is 38,984, 1,683 are CIS while 1,675 people are from abroad visited from countries. (Figure 1)

In 2020, according to the purpose of the trip, the hotel and so on number fund in similar places is 690 and placed the number of persons was 38,990. With personal goals if the number of placed persons was 7515, work of persons placed on the basis of and for professional purposes number was 31475 people.

In 2020, the number of hotels and similar means of accommodation was 39. 31 of them are hotels, 16.1% are one-star hotels, 6.5% are two-star hotels, 16.1% are three-star hotels, and 61.3% are uncategorized hotels.

It is aimed at a wide study of the touristic potential of the Jizzakh region, and the issues of wider use of the ecotourism opportunities of the region, and promising projects for attracting tourists.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Why is Jizzakh region attractive for foreign and local tourists?

- With its unique nature and unique historical monuments, architectural monuments, national identity and traditional cuisine, our region was not an exception for the rapid development of tourism. Today, this industry has become one of the promising directions of the region's development. Currently, 372 objects of cultural heritage are under state protection in the region, of which 42 are historical monuments, shrines, 267 are archaeological, and 63 are monuments. Nurota and Zomin nature reserves, Zomin National Nature Park, Aydar-Arnasoy lake system, 9 forest farms and desert areas of Kyzylkum are located in the region. In the region,

forests occupy an area of 72 thousand hectares, there are 50 species of animals and birds and 1000 species of plants.

What is the situation with infrastructure objects in the region, including residential buildings - hotels, hostels and hotel chains for foreign tourists? Representatives of which foreign countries often visit our region?

Currently, there are 91 accommodation facilities in the region that can serve more than 2500 people at the same time, 31 of them are 1-4 star hotels (1064 beds), 45 are guest houses. (391 places), 13 resorts, 2 camps and resorts (39 places). 85 places), as well as 5 tour operators. 4 tourist information centers (infokiosks) were established in the most visited places of the region.

RESULTS

Currently, not only in our country, but also in the whole world, the tourism industry is a low-labor, but profitable industry. This field is considered a supporter of some attractiveness, requiring appropriate culture, ethics, and aesthetics. In addition to the economic aspects of the tourism sector, it is necessary to highlight its social and spiritual aspects. That is, economically, there is a lot corresponding to 1 soum of labor there is an opportunity to earn income with less work compared to some that require labor, for example, the construction industry. From a social point of view, the service workers working in this field at the same time enjoy the products of this field while providing services to tourists, which in turn causes the extension of human life. Spiritually, through the development of the tourism sector, it is possible to strengthen the position of our country on the world map by showing off our architectural monuments, which are the symbols of our national values inherited from our ancestors, and our beautiful nature to the whole world. occurs.

It is known that the tourism sector is one of the most non-negotiable sectors in the world. That is why significant work is being done in our country to develop this sector, in particular, the Law "On Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on April 16, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 13, 2019 "Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5781 of January 5, 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for the further development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" " Decree No. PF-5611 was adopted, according to which the types of tourism, forms and their institutional basis are given, in some sources directions for the creation of tourist villages and its institutional basis, as well as in the cross-section of regions on the creation of tourist village zones [Aynakulov M.A. Khudaiberdiyev B.B, 2020] suggestions and recommendations are given.

DISCUSSION

The first is the institutional basis of organizing tourist guesthouses first of all, "Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan" adopted on April 16, 2019 on" Law, as well as 2019 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5781 dated August 13, "On measures to further develop the tourism sector in the Republic of Uzbekistan". Based on these institutional principles, starting from November 1, 2019, the formation of a list of citizens' assemblies (towns, villages, villages and neighborhoods of cities, towns, villages and villages) with the highest tourism potential, in the territories of these citizens' assemblies When not less than 20 family guesthouses are established and at least five different types of services are provided for tourists (except accommodation and/or food services), they are designated as "Tourism neighborhood", "Tourism village" or "Tourism ovuli" status, from 2020, citizens' gatherings with the status of

"Tourism Village", "Tourism Village" or "Tourism Village" should be included in the state programs "Prosperous Village" and "Prosperous Neighborhood" as a first priority. issued [Decree No. PF-5781 of August 13, 2019].

According to Article 5 of the Law "On Tourism of the Republic of Uzbekistan", international and domestic tourism are its forms. Organization of tourism the uniqueness, subject, duration, methods of movement and Based on other characteristics of the type, it can be divided into cultural-historical, pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, business, social, sports, medical, youth tourism, agrotourism and other types of tourism. [The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Tourism. On April 16, 2019 accepted].

CONCLUSIONS

Complex measures for the development of the tourism sector as one of the strategic industries are being implemented step by step in our country.

Also, rapid development of domestic tourism as one of the most important factors of sustainable socio-economic development of regions, introducing tourists to cultural-historical heritage and natural resources of our country, regional brands that attract tourists with their charm, liberalization of the visa regime as its basis, simplifying the procedure of registration of foreign citizens, providing privileges and preferences for the development of the tourism network will allow effective promotion of national tourism potential in domestic and foreign markets.

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